

Management of Child Contacts of Tuberculosis Cases in Resource-Constrained Areas:
Prospective Validation of World Health Organization's Pragmatic Guidelines
from a High-Burden, sub-Saharan African Setting

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ABSTRACT.

BACKGROUND.

Tuberculosis is a leading cause of global childhood mortality, however interventions to detect undiagnosed children are underutilized. Child contact tracing has been widely recommended but poorly implemented in resource-constrained settings. The World Health Organization (WHO) released a pragmatic, symptom-based screening approach for managing child contacts. We evaluated the effectiveness of this guideline and alternative algorithms in identifying secondary tuberculosis from a prospectively followed Ugandan child contact cohort.

METHODS.

Coprevalent and incident tuberculosis was evaluated in household contacts through clinical, radiographical, and microbiological examinations for two years. Disease rates were compared among children <16 years old with and without symptoms included in the WHO pragmatic guideline (presence of hemoptysis, fever, chronic cough, weight loss, night sweats, poor appetite). Symptoms were of any duration except cough (>21 days) and fever (>14 days). A modified algorithm designed to detect high-risk asymptomatic child contacts was also evaluated.

FINDINGS.

Of 1718 children, 126 (7.3%) and 24 (1.5%) contacts had coprevalent and incident tuberculosis; 63% were culture-confirmed. Among children with and without symptoms, coprevalent tuberculosis was 23.4% compared to 3.0% ($P<0.0001$). Children recommended for screening had more coprevalent disease when restricting the study population by HIV-serostatus, age, or to only culture-confirmed cases. In a modified algorithm, high-risk asymptomatic child contacts were at increased risk for coprevalent disease (6.3% versus 2.4% in low-risk asymptomatics, $P<0.01$). The presence of

tuberculosis infection did not predict primary progressive disease in either symptomatic or asymptomatic child contacts.

INTERPRETATION.

WHO's pragmatic, symptom-based algorithm was an effective case-finding tool, especially in children <5 years old. A modified decision-tree identified asymptomatic child contacts at high-risk (6%) for subclinical disease. Increasing feasibility of child contact tracing using these approaches should be encouraged to decrease tuberculosis-related pediatric mortality in high-burden settings.

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INTRODUCTION.

Tuberculosis is a leading cause of global childhood mortality,¹ however screening interventions to detect undiagnosed children are underutilized.²⁻⁴ This is especially clear in high-burden settings where limited health resources have largely concentrated on diagnosing adults with smear-positive tuberculosis.^{5,6} As a consequence, case detection of tuberculosis in children is poor in these settings with recent reports estimating that two-thirds of pediatric cases are unreported and undiagnosed globally.⁷ These detection rates are especially concerning because untreated children with tuberculosis have mortality rates >20%.⁸ If treated, however, children are very likely to survive^{8,9} suggesting that improving case detection and treatment may decrease childhood mortality.

Household tracing of child contacts has been widely recommended by global health organizations and disease experts for over a decade¹⁰⁻¹² because child contacts have a high yield of both *Mycobacterium tuberculosis* infection and disease.¹³⁻¹⁶ Despite this, contact tracing has been implemented poorly or not at all in high-burden, low-income settings.^{11,17} For example, <20% of contacts of tuberculosis patients diagnosed in Ethiopia were programmatically screened for disease.¹⁸ As a consequence, a large proportion, at times >90%,¹⁹ of child contacts eligible for preventive therapy are unidentified by tuberculosis control services.²⁰ In low-incidence settings, provision of isoniazid preventive therapy is considered “standard of care” and is largely implemented. In high-incidence settings, programmatic implementation of tracing household-exposed children has been difficult due to their resource intensiveness and limited access to diagnostic tests, including radiographical imaging, microbiological examinations, and tuberculin skin testing.^{3,17,21,22} Alternative screening approaches to

detect childhood tuberculosis, that can be implemented in high-burden settings, are needed to increase case detection and prevent progression to disease.

In an attempt to make implementation of child contact tracing more feasible, the World Health Organization (WHO) published pragmatic guidelines based on symptoms for the management of child contacts of tuberculosis cases in high-burden settings in 2006 and updated these in 2014.^{10,23,24} These guidelines state that child contacts of tuberculosis cases should be screened for tuberculosis using a set of tuberculosis-specific symptoms chosen to discriminate disease from infection. Based on the presence of symptoms, children may be treated for disease if diagnosed or offered preventive therapy for presumed tuberculosis infection, especially for the very young or immunocompromised. This symptom-based approach may be a more feasible and efficient programmatic avenue for National Tuberculosis Programs with limited resources or without access to diagnostic testing. Other groups have suggested modifications to the WHO guideline⁴ or evaluated alternative symptom-based algorithms^{25,26} in an attempt to improve the diagnostic performance of contact investigations at the programmatic level. Prospective validation of these recommendations has been limited²⁴ and the role of HIV infection has not been investigated. Whether these algorithms are useful in sub-Saharan Africa, where HIV is common and pediatric tuberculosis represents a large proportion of all cases,²⁷ remains uncertain.

To fill this knowledge gap, we estimated the concordance with the WHO guideline for secondary tuberculosis in a large, prospectively followed Ugandan cohort of child household contacts exposed to tuberculosis. We further evaluated two proposed alternative screening recommendations including a more expansive, modified WHO decision tree⁴ and a more restrictive algorithm.

METHODS.

STUDY POPULATION AND SETTING.

The study design has been described previously.^{15,28,29} Briefly, newly diagnosed pulmonary tuberculosis patients ≥ 18 years old were identified at Old Mulago Hospital in Kampala, Uganda from 1995–2008. Uganda is one of the 22 high-burden countries and the community prevalence of tuberculosis around Kampala has been previously reported to be as high as 1%.³⁰ Index cases were microbiologically-confirmed based on growth of *M. tuberculosis* in culture with at least one household contact and were evaluated through a physical examination and medical history.

Households of index tuberculosis cases were visited by field workers within two weeks of index case's diagnosis. A household was defined as a group of people living within one residence who shared meals together and identified a head of family who made decisions for the household. Contacts were defined as any individual spending at least seven consecutive days in the same household as the index case in the three months preceding diagnosis. Household members completed a baseline sociodemographic questionnaire and physical examination collecting data on age, sex, relationship to the index case, education level, past tuberculosis, and environmental characteristics. Bacillus Calmette-Guérin (BCG) vaccination was assessed through inspecting deltoid scars and then confirmed with medical records when available.

Index cases and contacts were offered HIV testing with an enzyme-linked immunosorbent assay (Cambridge Bioscience, Worcester, Massachusetts). This was performed after informed consent from parents/guardians and pre- and post-test counseling. Tuberculosis infection was identified with tuberculin skin testing (TST), performed by placing 0.1 ml of 5 tuberculin units of purified protein derivative (Tubersol,

Connaught Laboratories, Limited, Toronto, Canada) on the volar surface of the left forearm of each contact using the Mantoux method. Two field workers independently read the transverse diameter of palpable induration within 48–72 hours using digital calipers to reduce digit preference. Children with a tuberculin skin test indurations ≤ 5 millimeter were re-tested within 3 months; those testing positive on the second test were considered to be infected at baseline.

OUTCOME MEASUREMENTS AND DEFINITIONS.

Tuberculosis-Specific Outcomes.

The diagnosis of childhood tuberculosis in this study has been described elsewhere^{15,29} and further details are available in the supplementary appendix. Briefly, all household contacts were evaluated for tuberculosis through a medical examination and anteroposterior chest radiographs examined independently by two experienced pulmonary physicians. Specimen microscopy and mycobacterial culture were obtained if the child was under six years of age, symptomatic, had suggestive chest radiograph findings, clinical suspicion of tuberculosis, or HIV-seropositive. If a sputum sample could not be collected, alternative sites (including gastric aspiration, nasopharyngeal aspiration, pleural fluid, cerebrospinal fluid, and lymph node aspiration, as clinically indicated) were tested. Culture was performed (Lowenstein Jensen slants/BACTEC) in triplicate at the baseline evaluation, sick visits, and regular follow-up visits.

Classification of pulmonary tuberculosis was conducted using international consensus guidelines.³¹ Confirmed tuberculosis was defined as bacteriological confirmation from at least 1 respiratory specimen. Unconfirmed tuberculosis was defined as a clinical illness consistent with tuberculosis based on ≥ 2 of the following: results of chest radiography consistent with pulmonary tuberculosis, chest radiograph

consistent with tuberculosis, or a response to antituberculosis therapy. Unlikely tuberculosis was defined as children in which bacteriological confirmation was not obtained and criteria for “unconfirmed tuberculosis” not met. Coprevalent disease was defined as confirmed or unconfirmed tuberculosis identified at baseline or within three months; incident tuberculosis was defined as confirmed or unconfirmed that occurred after three months among contacts classified without coprevalent disease.³² Nine-month isoniazid prophylaxis was offered to disease-free child contacts if aged <5 years, HIV-infected, or if TST positive at enrollment. Adherence and completion of preventive therapy was monitored for clinical purposes only but not for the study. The cohort was followed at six-month intervals for two years.

Characteristics Included in World Health Organization Guidelines.

WHO guidelines state that child contacts with tuberculosis-related symptoms, including chronic cough, fever, night sweats, hemoptysis, weight loss, and loss of appetite (Supplementary Table 4), should be screened for tuberculosis and, if diagnosed, treated. Children without disease but below 5 years of age or immunocompromised should be offered isoniazid preventive therapy. Chronic cough was defined as a continuous, nonremitting cough present for >3 weeks. Fever was defined as body temperature of >38°C for 14 days, after exclusion of common causes such as malaria or pneumonia. Weight loss was defined as reporting of weight loss or failure to thrive with confirmatory evidence from the child’s growth chart. Hemoptysis was defined as the expectoration of blood. Night sweats and loss of appetite were self-reported from children and parents. “Asymptomatic” contacts include children with cough of <3 weeks duration and/or fever of <2 weeks duration; for this reason, we use quotations throughout the manuscript for this group.

STATISTICAL ANALYTICAL PLAN.

Evaluation of World Health Organization Guidelines.

Contacts were included in this analysis if they were <16 years of age. Coprevalent and incident tuberculosis was estimated among all child contacts and then separately for each included characteristic in the WHO algorithm using standard 2x2 contingency tables. The number of characteristics present in each child was calculated and disease outcomes were computed for contacts with each number. We evaluated the number needed to screen (NNS) to detect one coprevalent and incident case and the proportion of the total number of diseased cases detected by screening children included in the guidelines. HIV-serostatus was missing for a subset of children; in all analyses, we used a conservative approach assuming children with missing values were HIV-seronegative.

To assess the effectiveness in different subgroups, we stratified our cohort in several ways. First, child contacts were grouped by age (0–4 and 5–15 age groups) and algorithm effectiveness was evaluated in each separately. Second, to assess whether the symptom-based algorithm would effectively detect secondary disease in HIV-endemic and nonendemic settings, we evaluated coprevalent and incident tuberculosis in HIV-seropositive and seronegative child contacts separately. We stratified by HIV-serostatus and compared the yield of coprevalent and incident disease. Lastly, we conducted a secondary analysis using only culture-confirmed child cases instead of the more comprehensive diagnostic definition used in the primary analysis.

Two-sided *P* values and 95% confidence intervals were used to assess statistical significance in all analyses. When comparing the different approaches, we used either Pearson chi-squared or McNemar tests for the difference between two proportions. Cochran-Armitage tests were used to test for trends between disease outcomes and the

presence of multiple symptoms. Diagnostic odds ratios (OR) for coprevalent tuberculosis were calculated for each symptom individually, the presence of any symptom, and other relevant characteristics. Because ruling out active disease, avoiding inappropriately administering preventive therapy, is an important screening criterion, we also report the negative predictive value for each outcome using the algorithm.

Evaluation of Alternative Proposed Algorithms.

As a secondary analysis, we evaluated other symptom-based screening algorithms. A modified WHO decision tree⁴ suggests screening all symptomatic contacts regardless of age or immunocompetency; asymptomatic contacts are grouped into high-risk (<3 years old or immunocompromised) and low-risk (\geq 3 years old and immunocompetent) children. We also evaluated the effectiveness of a more restrictive, symptom-based approach (chronic cough with another tuberculosis-related symptom). For each approach, we calculated rates of coprevalent and incident tuberculosis in child contacts and the proportion of the total number of diseased cases detected.

Yield of HIV-testing in Contacts with an HIV-infected Source Case.

In these WHO guidelines, HIV testing and counseling is recommended among contacts with an HIV source case (Recommendation 24).²³ Because this recommendation is based on “very low-quality of evidence”, we compared the yield of HIV-testing in child contacts stratifying by the HIV-serostatus of the index case and the age of the contact.

ETHICAL CONSIDERATIONS.

The study protocol was reviewed and approved by the National HIV/AIDS Research Committee of Makerere University and the institutional review board at

University Hospitals Cleveland Medical Center. Informed consent was obtained for all index cases and household contacts. Parents or guardians of child contacts provided written consent in addition to verbal assent from the children.

RESULTS.

DEMOGRAPHIC CHARACTERISTICS.

In all, 3048 household contacts were enrolled in the study (Figure 1), of which 1718 were below 16 years of age and included in this analysis (further reference to contacts in the manuscript refers to these child contacts). Median age of index cases was 30 years old (interquartile range [IQR], 25–37) and half were male. After laboratory and clinical testing, 44% were HIV-seropositive, and 58% had lung cavitory disease. The median duration of cough was 90 days (IQR, 45–120). Median age of child contacts was 7 years old (IQR, 3–11). Most contacts were TST positive using either a ≥ 10 -millimeter (61.5%) or ≥ 5 -millimeter (71.2%) cutoff. Most child contacts were BCG vaccinated (77%) (Table 1).

After baseline clinical examinations and microbiological testing, 126 contacts (7.3%) were diagnosed with coprevalent disease; after two-year follow-up, 24 children (1.5%) were diagnosed with incident tuberculosis. One child was diagnosed with extrapulmonary tuberculosis. Among incident cases, date of diagnosis was available for 17 incident cases; 10 (58.8%) were diagnosed in the first year of follow-up while 7 (41.2%) after one year. Of these 150 cases, 95 (63.3%) were microbiologically confirmed with a positive sputum culture. Among 1592 child contacts without baseline tuberculosis, information about preventive therapy was known in 1060 children (67%), of whom 563 contacts were administered preventive therapy. Of these contacts, 554 (98.5%) remained tuberculosis-free over follow-up. Preventive therapy was administered in 60% and 52% of contacts < 5 years of age and HIV-seropositive children, respectively.

TUBERCULOSIS-RELATED OUTCOMES STRATIFIED BY WORLD HEALTH ORGANIZATION'S PRAGMATIC GUIDELINE.

364 children (21.2% of 1718 child contacts) fulfilled WHO criteria for tuberculosis screening (Table 2, Supplementary Table 1). The most common characteristic was chronic cough (n=254, 14.8%). Of 1414 child contacts (82.3% of the cohort) tested for HIV, 54 (3.8%) tested positive. The clinical characteristics of children with disease were similar regardless of whether they were identified by the WHO guideline or not, except that children recommended for screening were younger ($P=0.005$) and more likely to have an HIV-seropositive mother ($P=0.015$).

Baseline Assessment.

Coprevalent tuberculosis ranged from 16.7% in child contacts with hemoptysis (OR, 2.9, 95% CI, 0.3–24.7) to 33.3% for those with weight loss (OR, 8.5, 95% CI, 5.3–13.4) (Table 2). Among child contacts with tuberculosis-related symptoms, 23.4% (N=85 of 364 child contacts) had coprevalent pulmonary tuberculosis (OR, 9.8, 95% CI, 6.8–14.5) (Figure 2). In the overall sample, the NNS to detect one coprevalent case was 13.7 children. Among child contacts recommended for screening using the algorithm, the NNS to detect one case was 4.3, whereas among contacts not recommended for screening, the NNS was 33.9 ($P<0.0001$).

Using the WHO approach, 23.4% of child contacts would be screened and 68% of coprevalent cases detected. The negative predictive value to detect coprevalent tuberculosis was 97.1% (95% CI, 96.2–97.7, Supplementary Table 3). The guideline was effective in contacts <5 years old; 33.3% had coprevalent disease compared to 6.3% amongst young children who did not have the guideline characteristics (both $P<0.0001$; Figure 3). However, the differences in coprevalent disease were also present among children ≥ 5 years old (9.8% versus 1.8%, $P<0.0001$).

The guideline successfully identified disease outcomes in both HIV-seropositive and seronegative child contacts (Figure 4). Among 54 HIV-seropositive child contacts, 23 contacts were symptomatic of whom 11 (47.8%) had coprevalent tuberculosis. Among 31 “asymptomatic” HIV-seropositive contacts, 6.5% had baseline disease ($P<0.0001$).

Upon restricting our diagnostic definition of tuberculosis to only culture-confirmed disease (Supplementary Figure 1), ninety-five children were diagnosed. For coprevalent disease, 47 children (12.9%) with tuberculosis-related symptoms had confirmed disease compared to 29 children (2.1%) without symptoms ($P<0.0001$).

Diagnosed Tuberculosis Over Follow-up.

In children <5 years of age or HIV-seropositive without baseline tuberculosis (N=511), 9 (1.8%) developed tuberculosis over follow-up. Incident tuberculosis occurred in 2 of 41 (4.8%) HIV-seropositive contacts (1 of 12 symptomatic HIV-seropositive contacts and 1 of 29 “asymptomatic” child contacts). Among disease-free child contacts with tuberculosis-related symptoms, 4.9% (N=15 of 395 contacts) developed disease over follow-up. Among children without symptoms, nine developed tuberculosis (9/1324, 0.7%). Tuberculosis infection had a minor influence on the development of incident disease in our study population (Figure 1). In symptomatic contacts, 5.4% infected contacts developed incident tuberculosis whereas 4.7% uninfected contacts developed disease ($P=0.80$). Amongst “asymptomatic” contacts, incident tuberculosis rates were 0.8% versus 0.8% amongst contacts infected and uninfected at baseline, respectively ($P=1.0$).

When using only microbiological confirmation for pediatric diagnosis, 12 children would be classified as developing disease during follow-up. Seven of these children were symptomatic while 5 were “asymptomatic”.

EVALUATION OF TWO ALTERNATIVE SYMPTOM-BASED ALGORITHMS.

Upon evaluating a modified WHO decision-treat⁴ that groups “asymptomatic” contacts into high- and low-risk groups (Figure 5), 224 were high-risk and “asymptomatic” and 1131 were low-risk and “asymptomatic”. Symptomatic contacts were at highest-risk for disease (23.4% [NNS, 4.3] and 5% [NNS, 20] coprevalent and incident disease; $P<0.05$ versus both other groupings). High-risk “asymptomatic” contacts had higher rates of coprevalent disease compared to low-risk “asymptomatic” children (6.3% [NNS, 15.9] versus 2.4% [NNS, 41.7], $P<0.01$) but similar rates of incident disease (1.4% [NNS, 71.4] versus 0.6% [NNS, 166.7], $P_{exact}=0.23$). If both symptomatic and high-risk “asymptomatic” contacts were screened and followed-up, 78.6% and 70.8% and of all coprevalent and incident cases would be evaluated (Supplementary Table 4).

When using a more restrictive symptom algorithm, only 108 child contacts would have been screened compared to the 395 from the main analysis or 587 for the modified WHO algorithm that includes both symptomatic and high-risk “asymptomatic” children. Compared to the WHO approach, this algorithm would detect a higher disease-yield (31.5% [NNS, 3.2] versus 23.4% [NNS, 4.3], $P_{McNemar}<0.01$), but substantially fewer number of the total coprevalent disease burden (27% versus 68%, $P<0.0001$). Similar results were seen for incident disease (9.5% versus 4.9% disease yield, $P=0.13$; 29.2% versus 62.5% of total number of cases, $P<0.0001$).

HIV-SEROPOSITIVITY IN CHILD CONTACTS OF HIV-SEROPOSITIVE INDEX CASES.

HIV infection was found almost exclusively (89% of all HIV-seropositive contacts) in child contacts of HIV-seropositive tuberculosis cases (47/624, 7.8% versus 6/756, 0.8% in child contacts of HIV-seronegative cases; Supplementary Figures 2 and 3). This relationship was magnified in contacts <10 years old (10.4% versus 0.3% for <5 years old, $P<0.0001$; 9.6% versus 1.3% for 5–9 years old, $P<0.0001$). Contacts ≥ 10 years of age with an HIV-seropositive index case were not at increased risk of HIV-infection (2.8% versus 1.0%, $P=0.29$).

DISCUSSION.

Pediatric deaths from tuberculosis occur largely due to a lack of validated and implementable health interventions to identify undiagnosed children in high-burden settings.¹ In this large prospective cohort study among 1718 Ugandan child contacts of tuberculosis cases, we found that screening only child contacts using a symptom-based approach recently recommended by the WHO detected ~70% of coprevalent child contacts while screening 22% of all children. The yield of coprevalent tuberculosis in children identified by the guideline was higher in all subgroups, including HIV-seropositive and seronegative children as well as very young children and adolescents. Incident tuberculosis was higher in child contacts identified by the guideline and when stratified by several important subgroups. Lastly, we evaluated a modified algorithm that attempted to identify high-risk “asymptomatic” contacts and found that >6% of this group presented with coprevalent disease in our study population.

Few previous studies have evaluated WHO guidelines for household contact tracing of children.^{24,33} Our study extends findings from earlier studies in several ways. First, symptomatic contacts had higher rates of secondary disease in both HIV-seropositive and seronegative contacts, suggesting usefulness in settings with varying burdens of HIV. Second, in our study, the algorithm was effective among children with microbiologically-confirmed disease. A larger proportion (>60%) of child cases in our study were confirmed microbiologically through sputum culture than other pediatric tuberculosis studies. This was the result of a systematic, protocol-driven approach that collected culture samples at multiple sites and time points, performed culture in triplicate, and used an inclusive criterion for microbiological testing. In previous validation studies, and in most studies investigating childhood tuberculosis, tuberculosis

was exclusively diagnosed either clinically or radiographically which has limited specificity. Other than young age, there were no significant differences between diagnosed pediatric tuberculosis cases with and without tuberculosis-related symptoms suggesting this algorithm may detect very young children who are notoriously difficult to diagnose microbiologically.

Previous studies evaluating this guideline diagnosed a low number of incident cases²⁴ or had a cross-sectional study design.³³ We diagnosed a total of 24 incident cases after two years of follow-up. Our study was not designed to estimate the efficacy of isoniazid preventive therapy so there may be confounding by indication where contacts offered and accepted preventive therapy were at highest-risk for primary progressive disease. This may have underestimated incident tuberculosis among symptomatic children in our main analysis and among high-risk “asymptomatic” child contacts in the modified WHO decision tree analysis. Due to ethical reasons, offering and providing preventive therapy in this hyperendemic setting was necessary.

This WHO guideline is pragmatic in nature and therefore imperfect. Other symptom-based diagnostic algorithms have also been proposed for childhood tuberculosis to optimize contact tracing. To prioritize the identification of “asymptomatic” child contacts at high-risk for coperivalent and primary progressive disease, Marais and colleagues proposed a modification to the WHO guideline.⁴ We found that 6% of high-risk “asymptomatic” children had coperivalent disease and that if both symptomatic and high-risk “asymptomatic” children were screened almost 8 in 10 secondary cases would be evaluated. For national and subnational tuberculosis programs with sufficient resources this approach may be beneficial and detect high-risk children with low-chances of diagnosis through current screening measures. A more restrictive symptom-based algorithm was also evaluated. Unsurprisingly, this algorithm is more effective in

detecting coprevalent and incident disease as it restricts screening to only the highest risk contacts. However, when using this approach our results suggest a sizeable proportion of child contacts would be left undiagnosed. There is no “one size fits all” approach for childhood case detection as National Tuberculosis Programs have distinct health resources and childhood tuberculosis epidemics. We present results from all proposed algorithms of which we are aware and suggest local disease dynamics may need to be evaluated alongside these results.³⁴

Alarming levels, above 10%, of HIV-seropositivity in contacts of HIV-seropositive index cases were found in children <10 years old. This association with young age is likely due to mother-to-child HIV transmission. This result highlights the need for integrated tuberculosis and HIV management, HIV-testing among high-risk children and pregnant women, and antiretroviral therapy in pregnant women.

In 2014, there were an estimated 7.5 million household child contacts globally³⁵ representing a large pool of children at high-risk for primary progressive disease and death.^{13,36} These results suggest the WHO’s symptom-based approach,^{10,23} or a modified decision tree,⁴ may be useful in resource-constrained settings to improve implementation of contact tracing. Symptoms can be evaluated without specialized clinicians, little information is needed to inform if further evaluation or treatment is necessary, and most information can be validly self-reported by parents/guardians. Cost-effectiveness analyses may be useful to further inform policy³⁷ however, in our study population, very few contacts needed to be screened to detect a single case (NNS, 4.5) compared to screening all child contacts under the proposed approach suggesting high resource-efficiency.

Although these algorithms may be useful today in addressing the problem of pediatric tuberculosis in resource-constrained settings, their performance characteristics

can and should be improved. Symptomatology algorithms suffer from the classical trade-offs between sensitivity and specificity. As symptoms become less inclusive, sensitivity worsens but specificity improves; and conversely, as symptoms become more inclusive, sensitivity improves but specificity worsens. The current repertoire of diagnostic testing is unlikely to improve household contact investigations because they are expensive or unavailable (i.e., GeneXpert, chest radiography, TST, or interferon-gamma assays) in the many clinics that must handle contact evaluations.^{22,23} Accurate and reliable point-of-care diagnostic tests that can be readily used and implemented in resource-constrained settings are urgently needed to improve household case detection of children.³⁸ If access to high-quality diagnostic tools improves, the proposed algorithms may be able to achieve greater effectiveness.

There are limitations to this analysis. A proportion of children were missing HIV data. We used a cautious approach assuming all children with missing values were HIV-seronegative. Although most symptoms were validated, others, such as night sweats and poor appetite, were self-reported and may be subject to social desirability and recall biases. This bias would likely bring the association between our analyses and tuberculosis outcomes towards the null. Tuberculosis diagnosis in an asymptomatic exposed child with a culture-confirmed test is an area of open debate in the literature (especially if chest radiographical examinations are clear). Theoretically, if these children do not actually have tuberculosis and are in some other stage of the disease spectrum (i.e., tuberculosis infection), as suggested by some, this would bias our evaluations of these algorithms towards the null.³⁹ In the analysis of incident disease, it is possible that differential loss to follow-up may introduce a selection bias in the analysis.

Lastly, our findings may be distinct to those found in communities from low tuberculosis and/or HIV burden settings. However, tuberculosis and HIV prevalence is high in many African and low-income countries; poor nutrition and socioeconomic status were common in our study population and are ubiquitous across sub-Saharan African communities suggesting these results may be applicable to other high tuberculosis prevalence areas in Africa.

In conclusion, a symptom-based, algorithm approach²³ and a modified decision tree⁴ detected approximately 70% and 80% of all secondary disease in Ugandan child contacts despite screening a small proportion of contacts. This approach may be useful in resource-constrained settings to improve implementation of child contact tracing but should be partnered with increasing access to microbiological point-of-care testing.

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CONFLICTS OF INTEREST.

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REFERENCES.

1. Dodd P, Yuen C, Sismanidis C, Seddon J, Jenkins H. The global burden of tuberculosis mortality in children: a mathematical modelling study. *Lancet Global Health*. 2017.
2. du Cros P, Nyang'wa BT, Gale M, Venis S, Ford N. Counting children: comparing reporting for paediatric HIV and tuberculosis. *Bulletin of the World Health Organization*. 2011;89(12):855.
3. Hill PC, Rutherford ME, Audas R, van Crevel R, Graham SM. Closing the policy-practice gap in the management of child contacts of tuberculosis cases in developing countries. *PLoS medicine*. 2011;8(10):e1001105.
4. Marais BJ, Pai M. New approaches and emerging technologies in the diagnosis of childhood tuberculosis. *Paediatric respiratory reviews*. 2007;8(2):124-133.
5. Maher D, Chaulet P, Spinaci S, Harries A. *For World Health Organisation. Global Tuberculosis Programme. Treatment of Tuberculosis: Guidelines for National Programmes. 2. baski*. WHO/TB/97.220, Geneva;1997.
6. Borgdorff MW, Floyd K, Broekmans JF. Interventions to reduce tuberculosis mortality and transmission in low-and middle-income countries. *Bulletin of the World Health Organization*. 2002;80(3):217-227.
7. Dodd PJ, Gardiner E, Coghlan R, Seddon JA. Burden of childhood tuberculosis in 22 high-burden countries: a mathematical modelling study. *The lancet global health*. 2014;2(8):e453-e459.
8. Jenkins HE, Yuen CM, Rodriguez CA, et al. Mortality in children diagnosed with tuberculosis: a systematic review and meta-analysis. *The Lancet. Infectious diseases*. 2017;17(3):285-295.
9. Osman M, Lee K, Du Preez K, Dunbar R, Hesselning AC, Seddon JA. Excellent treatment outcomes in children treated for tuberculosis under routine operational conditions in Cape Town. *Clinical Infectious Diseases*. 2017.
10. World Health Organization. Guidance for national tuberculosis programmes on the management of tuberculosis in children. 2006.
11. Graham SM, Triasih R. More evidence to support screening of child contacts of tuberculosis cases: if not now, then when? *Clinical infectious diseases*. 2013:cit647.
12. Hsu KH. Contact Investigation: A Practical Approach to Tuberculosis Eradication. *American journal of public health and the nation's health*. 1963;53:1761-1769.
13. Morrison J, Pai M, Hopewell PC. Tuberculosis and latent tuberculosis infection in close contacts of people with pulmonary tuberculosis in low-income and middle-income countries: a systematic review and meta-analysis. *The Lancet. Infectious diseases*. 2008;8(6):359-368.
14. Martinez L, Shen Y, Mupere E, Kizza A, Hill PC, Whalen CC. Transmission of Mycobacterium Tuberculosis in Households and the Community: A Systematic Review and Meta-Analysis. *Am J Epidemiol*. 2017:1-13.
15. Jaganath D, Zalwango S, Okware B, et al. Contact investigation for active tuberculosis among child contacts in Uganda. *Clinical infectious diseases : an official publication of the Infectious Diseases Society of America*. 2013;57(12):1685-1692.

16. Mandalakas AM, Ngo K, Ustero PA, et al. BUTIMBA: Intensifying the Hunt for Child TB in Swaziland through Household Contact Tracing. *PloS one*. 2017;12(1):e0169769.
17. Rutherford ME, Ruslami R, Anselmo M, et al. Management of children exposed to Mycobacterium tuberculosis: a public health evaluation in West Java, Indonesia. *Bulletin of the World Health Organization*. 2013;91(12):932-941a.
18. Gebregergs GB, Alemu WG. Household contact screening adherence among tuberculosis patients in Northern Ethiopia. *PloS one*. 2015;10(5):e0125767.
19. Van Wyk SS, Reid AJ, Mandalakas AM, et al. Operational challenges in managing isoniazid preventive therapy in child contacts: a high-burden setting perspective. *BMC public health*. 2011;11(1):544.
20. World Health Organization. Global tuberculosis report 2016. 2016.
21. Rutherford ME, Hill PC, Triasih R, Sinfield R, van Crevel R, Graham SM. Preventive therapy in children exposed to Mycobacterium tuberculosis: problems and solutions. *Trop Med Int Health*. 2012;17(10):1264-1273.
22. Pande T, Pai M, Khan FA, Denkinger CM. Use of chest radiography in the 22 highest tuberculosis burden countries. *European Respiratory Journal*. 2015:ERJ-01064-02015.
23. *World Health Organization. Guidance for national tuberculosis programmes on the management of tuberculosis in children*. World Health Organization; 2014.
24. Triasih R, Robertson CF, Duke T, Graham SM. A prospective evaluation of the symptom-based screening approach to the management of children who are contacts of tuberculosis cases. *Clinical infectious diseases : an official publication of the Infectious Diseases Society of America*. 2015;60(1):12-18.
25. Bonnet M, Kyakwera C, Kyomugasho N, et al. Prospective cohort study of the feasibility and yield of household child tuberculosis contact screening in Uganda. *The International Journal of Tuberculosis and Lung Disease*. 2017;21(8):862-868.
26. Egere U, Togun T, Sillah A, et al. Identifying children with tuberculosis among household contacts in The Gambia. *The international journal of tuberculosis and lung disease : the official journal of the International Union against Tuberculosis and Lung Disease*. 2017;21(1):46-52.
27. Donald PR. Childhood tuberculosis: out of control? *Current opinion in pulmonary medicine*. 2002;8(3):178-182.
28. Martinez L, Sekandi JN, Castellanos ME, Zalwango S, Whalen CC. Infectiousness of HIV-seropositive patients with tuberculosis in a high-burden African setting. *American journal of respiratory and critical care medicine*. 2016;194(9):1152-1163.
29. Martinez L, Handel A, Shen Y, et al. A Prospective Validation of a Clinical Algorithm to Detect Tuberculosis in Child Contacts. *American journal of respiratory and critical care medicine*. 2017(ja).
30. Guwatudde D, Zalwango S, Kanya MR, et al. Burden of tuberculosis in Kampala, Uganda. *Bulletin of the World Health Organization*. 2003;81(11):799-805.
31. Graham SM, Cuevas LE, Jean-Philippe P, et al. Clinical case definitions for classification of intrathoracic tuberculosis in children: an update. *Clinical Infectious Diseases*. 2015;61(suppl_3):S179-S187.
32. Fox GJ, Barry SE, Britton WJ, Marks GB. Contact investigation for tuberculosis: a systematic review and meta-analysis. *European Respiratory Journal*. 2013;41(1):140-156.

33. Kruk A, Gie RP, Schaaf HS, Marais BJ. Symptom-based screening of child tuberculosis contacts: improved feasibility in resource-limited settings. *Pediatrics*. 2008;121(6):e1646-1652.
34. Theron G, Jenkins HE, Cobelens F, et al. Data for action: collection and use of local data to end tuberculosis. *Lancet (London, England)*. 2015;386(10010):2324-2333.
35. Yuen C, Jenkins H, Chang R, Mpunga J, Becerra M. Two methods for setting child-focused tuberculosis care targets. *Public health action*. 2016;6(2):83-96.
36. Gomes VF, Andersen A, Wejse C, et al. Impact of tuberculosis exposure at home on mortality in children under 5 years of age in Guinea-Bissau. *Thorax*. 2010:thx. 2010.141309.
37. Mandalakas AM, Hesselning AC, Gie RP, Schaaf H, Marais BJ, Sinanovic E. Modelling the cost-effectiveness of strategies to prevent tuberculosis in child contacts in a high-burden setting. *Thorax*. 2012:thoraxjnl-2011-200933.
38. Zar HJ, Connell TG, Nicol M. Diagnosis of pulmonary tuberculosis in children: new advances. *Expert review of anti-infective therapy*. 2010;8(3):277-288.
39. Loveday M, Sunkari B, Marais BJ, Master I, Brust JC. Dilemma of managing asymptomatic children referred with 'culture-confirmed' drug-resistant tuberculosis. *Archives of disease in childhood*. 2016;101(7):608-613.

TABLES.

Table 1. Demographic Characteristics of 1718 Household Child Contacts of Tuberculosis Cases.

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FIGURES.

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Table 1. Demographic Characteristics of 1718 Household Child Contacts of Tuberculosis Cases.

Variable	Frequency	Percent*
Household contact characteristics		
N	1718	100
Median age, years (IQR)	7 (3 – 11)	–
Age group, years		
0 – 4	578	33.6
5 – 15	1140	66.4
Male sex	582	48.3
BCG vaccinated††	1325	77.1
Exposure to Another Tuberculosis Case†	161	9.4
Relation to index case		
Child	1028	59.8
Sibling	104	6.1
Other ^c	571	33.2
Missing	15	0.9
Past tuberculosis	11	0.6
Closeness to index case		
Share bed	192	11.2
Share room, not bed	896	52.2
Different room	610	35.5
Missing	20	1.2
Index case characteristics‡		
Median age, years (IQR)	30 (25 – 37)	–
Age group, years		
18 – 29	789	45.9
30 – 39	589	34.3
40 – 49	238	13.9
≥50	75	4.4
Male sex	795	47.0
Cigarette smoker	302	17.6
Cavitory disease§	992	57.7
Median cough duration, days (IQR)	90 (45 – 120)	–
HIV-seropositive	754	43.9
Household characteristics		
Housing type		
Multi-family household	834	48.5
Single family household	877	51.1
Missing	7	0.4
Charcoal or fire smoke exposure		
Inside household	372	21.7
Outside household	1262	73.5
None	57	3.3
Missing	27	1.6
Ventilation, ≤1 windows/room**	1532	89.2
Median density, persons/home (IQR)	6 (4 – 8)	–
Household size (persons/home)		
1 – 5	717	41.7

6 – 10	818	47.6
>10	183	10.7

Abbreviations: IQR, interquartile range. SD, standard deviation. BCG, bacillus Calmette-Guerin. HIV, human immunodeficiency virus.

* Percentages refer to within characteristic column totals among household contacts of tuberculosis index patients. Percentages may not total 100% because within column percentages were rounded to the nearest integer

† This refers to exposure to another tuberculosis case other than the index case in the previous twelve months before the baseline visit.

‡ These are the number and percent of household contacts exposed to the index case characteristic in the left-hand column.

§ Radiographic imaging results were graded by an experienced clinician using the 1961 National Tuberculosis Association classification system.

**Windows must be to the outside.

†† Evaluated through BCG scar, verified by medical records when available

Table 2. Yield of Coprevalent Tuberculosis in 1718 Household Child Contacts of Tuberculosis Cases, Stratified by the World Health Screening Guideline for the Management of Child Contacts§.

Variable	Total	Coprevalent tuberculosis†			
		Diseased Contacts (%)	NNS*	% all cases detected	Diagnostic Odds Ratio (95% CI)
All child contacts	1718	126 (7.3)	13.7	100	NA
World Health Organization's Pragmatic Guideline‡					
Poor appetite	52	13 (25.0)	4	10.3	4.7 (2.4, 9.0)
Chronic cough	254	60 (23.6)	4.2	47.6	6.6 (4.5, 9.7)
Weight loss	105	35 (33.3)	3	27.8	8.5 (5.3, 13.4)
Fever	114	35 (30.7)	3.3	27.8	7.4 (4.7, 11.6)
Night sweats	52	12 (23.1)	4.3	9.5	4.1 (2.1, 8.0)
Hemoptysis	7	1 (16.7)	6	0.8	2.9 (0.3, 24.7)
Children with ≥1 Tuberculosis-related Symptoms‡	364	85 (23.4)	4.3	68.0	9.8 (6.8, 14.5)
Number of Tuberculosis-related Symptoms‡					
0	1354	41 (3.0)	33.9	32.5	1 (Referent)
1	225	43 (19.1)	5.2	34.1	7.6 (4.8, 11.9)
2	80	22 (27.5)	3.6	17.5	12.1 (6.8, 21.7)
3	40	13 (32.5)	3.1	10.3	15.4 (7.4, 32.0)
4	17	5 (29.4)	3.4	4.0	13.3 (7.4, 32.0)
5	2	2 (100)	1	4.0	NA
Children with any symptom other than chronic cough & fever of >2 weeks	161	42 (26.1)	3.8	33.3	6.2 (4.1, 9.4)
Tuberculin skin test positive (≥5 mm)	1216	105 (8.6)	11.6	83.3	2.1 (1.3, 3.4)
Tuberculin skin test positive (≥10 mm)	1056	92 (8.7)	11.5	73	1.7 (1.2, 2.6)
HIV-seropositive	54	13 (24.1)	4.1	10.3	3.7 (1.9, 7.1)

Abbreviations. NNS, number needed to screen. No., number. mm, millimeter. CI, confidence interval. NA, not applicable.

† Coprevalent tuberculosis was defined as the identification of tuberculosis at or within 3 months of the baseline household visit. Incident tuberculosis was defined as diagnosis of tuberculosis at subsequent household follow-up visits,

conducted at 6-month intervals for 2 years. Individuals with coprevalent disease were excluded from analyses of incident disease

§ Participants with missing values for characteristics included in the World Health Organization guideline were assumed to not have the characteristic in our main analysis.

* This is the number of child contacts in the specified row that is needed to screen in order to detect one coprevalent tuberculosis case. This is calculated by dividing 100 by the row-specific disease prevalence. For example, 7.3% of all child contacts had coprevalent tuberculosis. Therefore, 14 (13.7 is specified in this row) contacts need to be screened to detect one coprevalent tuberculosis case among the total child contact cohort (N=1718 child contacts).

‡ Participants were included in the pragmatic guideline if they had one tuberculosis-related symptom including chronic cough, fever, night sweats, hemoptysis, weight loss, and loss of appetite. Chronic cough was defined as a continuous, nonremitting cough present for >3 weeks. Fever was defined as body temperature of >38°C for 14 days, after exclusion of common causes such as malaria or pneumonia. Weight loss was defined as reporting of weight loss or failure to thrive with confirmatory evidence from the child's growth chart. Hemoptysis was defined as the expectoration of blood from the lung airways or parenchyma. Night sweats and loss of appetite were self-reported from children and parents.

“Asymptomatic” contacts included children with cough of <3 weeks duration and/or fever of <3 weeks duration.

Figure 1. Study Profile of Symptom-based Approaches Evaluated for Child Contact Investigation, Kampala, Uganda†.

†Symptomatic contacts included contacts with any tuberculosis-related symptom including chronic cough, fever, night sweats, hemoptysis, weight loss, and loss of appetite. Chronic cough was defined as a continuous, nonremitting cough present for >3 weeks. Fever was defined as body temperature of >38°C for 14 days, after exclusion of common causes

such as malaria or pneumonia. Weight loss was defined as reporting of weight loss or failure to thrive with confirmatory evidence from the child's growth chart. Hemoptysis was defined as the expectoration of blood from the lung airways or parenchyma. Night sweats and loss of appetite were self-reported from children and parents. "Asymptomatic" contacts included children with cough of <3 weeks duration and/or fever of <2 weeks duration.

Figure 2. Tuberculosis-related Outcomes§ Stratified by World Health Organization’s Symptom-based Approach for the Management of Child Contacts†

Abbreviations. TST, tuberculin skin test. mm, millimeters.

§ Coprevalent tuberculosis was defined as the identification of tuberculosis at or within 3 months of the baseline household visit. Incident tuberculosis was defined as diagnosis of tuberculosis at subsequent household follow-up visits, conducted at 6-month intervals for 2 years. Individuals with coprevalent disease were excluded from analyses of incident disease. In this analysis, latent tuberculosis was defined as a tuberculin skin test induration response of ≥ 10 millimeters. Percentages may not total 100% because within-characteristic percentages were rounded to the nearest integer.

† Participants were included in the pragmatic guideline if they had one tuberculosis-related symptom including chronic cough, fever, night sweats, hemoptysis, weight loss, and loss of appetite. Chronic cough was defined as a continuous,

nonremitting cough present for >3 weeks. Fever was defined as body temperature of >38°C for 14 days, after exclusion of common causes such as malaria or pneumonia. Weight loss was defined as reporting of weight loss or failure to thrive with confirmatory evidence from the child's growth chart. Hemoptysis was defined as the expectoration of blood from the lung airways or parenchyma. Night sweats and loss of appetite were self-reported from children and parents.

"Asymptomatic" contacts included children with cough of <3 weeks duration and/or fever of <2 weeks duration. The difference between coprevalent tuberculosis among symptomatic and "asymptomatic" contacts was statistically different (23.4% versus 3.0%, $P<0.0001$). Contacts with tuberculosis infection (tuberculin skin test induration ≥ 10 millimeters) did not result in increased risk for incident tuberculosis (amongst symptomatic contacts, 5.4% versus 4.7% incident tuberculosis rates amongst contacts infected and uninfected at baseline, $P=0.80$; amongst "asymptomatic" contacts, 0.8% versus 0.8% incident tuberculosis rates amongst contacts infected and uninfected at baseline, $P=1.0$)

Figure 3. Tuberculosis-related outcomes§ in Children Screened Following the World Health Organization Symptom-based Approach for the Management of Child Contacts, Stratified by the Age of the Child†

§ Coprevalent tuberculosis was defined as the identification of tuberculosis at or within 3 months of the baseline household visit. Incident tuberculosis was defined as diagnosis of tuberculosis at subsequent household follow-up visits, conducted at 6-month intervals for 2 years. Individuals with coprevalent disease were excluded from analyses of incident disease. In this figure, “Tuberculosis free” indicates contacts free of tuberculosis; these contacts may have tuberculosis infection. Percentages may not total 100% because within-characteristic percentages were rounded to the nearest integer.

† Participants were included in the pragmatic guideline if they had one tuberculosis-related symptom including chronic cough, fever, night sweats, hemoptysis, weight loss, and loss of appetite. Chronic cough was defined as a continuous, nonremitting cough present for >3 weeks. Fever was defined as body temperature of >38°C for 14 days, after exclusion of common causes such as malaria or pneumonia. Weight loss was defined as reporting of weight loss or failure to thrive with confirmatory evidence from the child's growth chart. Hemoptysis was defined as the expectoration of blood from the lung airways or parenchyma. Night sweats and loss of appetite were self-reported from children and parents. "Asymptomatic" contacts included children with cough of <3 weeks duration and/or fever of <2 weeks duration. The difference between coprevalent tuberculosis among symptomatic and "asymptomatic" contacts was statistically different for children <5 years of age (33.2% versus 6.3%, $P<0.0001$) and ≥ 5 years of age (9.8% versus 1.8%, $P<0.0001$).

Figure 4. Tuberculosis-related outcomes§ in Children Screened Following the World Health Organization Symptom-based Approach for the Management of Child Contacts, Stratified by the HIV-serostatus of the Child†.

§ Coprevalent tuberculosis was defined as the identification of tuberculosis at or within 3 months of the baseline household visit. Incident tuberculosis was defined as diagnosis of tuberculosis at subsequent household follow-up visits, conducted at 6-month intervals for 2 years. Individuals with coprevalent disease were excluded from analyses of incident disease. In this figure, “Tuberculosis free” indicates contacts free of tuberculosis; these contacts may have tuberculosis

infection. Percentages may not total 100% because within-characteristic percentages were rounded to the nearest integer.

† In this flowchart, infants with tuberculosis-related symptoms (including chronic cough, fever, night sweats, hemoptysis, weight loss, and loss of appetite,) were included to be screened in the algorithm. Chronic cough was defined as a continuous, nonremitting cough present for >3 weeks. Fever was defined as body temperature of >38°C for 14 days, after exclusion of common causes such as malaria or pneumonia. Weight loss was defined as reporting of weight loss or failure to thrive with confirmatory evidence from the child's growth chart. Hemoptysis was defined as the expectoration of blood from the lung airways or parenchyma. Night sweats and loss of appetite were self-reported from children and parents. "Asymptomatic" contacts included children with cough of <3 weeks duration and/or fever of <2 weeks duration. This analysis included 1414 child contacts that took an HIV test. The difference between coprevalent tuberculosis among symptomatic and "asymptomatic" contacts was statistically different for in HIV-seropositive children (47.8% versus 6.5%, $P<0.0001$) and HIV-seronegative children (22.6% versus 3.5%, $P<0.0001$).

Figure 5. Tuberculosis-related Outcomes§ in Children Screened Following a Modified World Health Organization Decision-Tree† Grouping Asymptomatic Child Contacts into High- and Low-risk Groups‡.

§ Coprevalent tuberculosis was defined as the identification of tuberculosis at or within 3 months of the baseline household visit. Incident tuberculosis was defined as diagnosis of tuberculosis at subsequent household follow-up visits, conducted at 6-month intervals for 2 years. Individuals with coprevalent disease were excluded from analyses of incident disease. In this figure, “Tuberculosis free” indicates contacts free of tuberculosis; these contacts may have tuberculosis infection. Percentages may not total 100% because within-characteristic percentages were rounded to the nearest integer.

† This algorithm was first proposed in the 2007 manuscript: Marais, B.J. and Pai, M., 2007. New approaches and emerging technologies in the diagnosis of childhood tuberculosis. *Paediatric respiratory reviews*, 8(2), pp.124-133. It was later proposed again in the 2010 manuscript: Marais, B.J. and Schaaf, H.S., 2010. Childhood tuberculosis: an emerging and previously neglected problem. *Infectious disease clinics of North America*, 24(3), pp.727-749.

‡ Children with tuberculosis-related symptoms is shown in Figure 2 and included children with either chronic cough, fever, night sweats, hemoptysis, weight loss, or loss of appetite. Chronic cough was defined as a continuous, nonremitting cough present for >3 weeks. Fever was defined as body temperature of >38°C for 14 days, after exclusion of common causes such as malaria or pneumonia. Weight loss was defined as reporting of weight loss or failure to thrive with confirmatory evidence from the child’s growth chart. Hemoptysis was defined as the expectoration of blood from the lung airways or parenchyma. Night sweats and loss of appetite were self-reported from children and parents. “Asymptomatic” contacts included children with cough of <3 weeks duration and/or fever of <2 weeks duration. This modified decision-tree, which proposes to group “asymptomatic” contacts into high- and low-risk groups, symptomatic contacts were at highest-risk for disease (23.4% and 5% coprevalent and incident disease; $P<0.05$ versus both other groupings). High-risk “asymptomatic contacts” had higher rates of coprevalent disease compared to low-risk “asymptomatics” (6.3% versus 2.4%, $P<0.01$) and similar rates of incident disease (1.4% versus 0.6%, $P_{exact}=0.23$). If both symptomatic and high-risk “asymptomatic” contacts were screened and followed-up, 78.6% and 70.8% and of all coprevalent and incident cases would be evaluated.